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Vitamin C for the common cold and pneumonia

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<https://scholar.google.fi/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

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This supplement describes the source for certain details, some new calculations, and selected related references for reviews.

Contents	Page
Reviews on the immune system and biochemistry	2
Statistical issues	3
Source of data and P-values for Table 2	6
Calculation of NNT for Table 3	13
Cox regression analysis of the COVID A to Z trial for Figure 3	14
Calculation of mid-P values for the pneumonia treatment trials	15
Variations in vitamin C levels in the control and vitamin C groups: data for Figure 5	16

Estimation of plasma vitamin C levels from reported dietary and urinary vitamin C levels	22
Alfred Hess and the risk of pneumonia in vitamin C deficiency	27
James Lind and respiratory infections in vitamin C deficiency	31
Albert Szent-Gyorgyi and pneumonia	32
References to the paper with additional links and extra references	33

Reviews on the immune system and biochemistry

In our review, we focus on clinically relevant outcomes, following the evidence-based medicine approach. Biochemical and immunological explanations do not determine whether vitamin C actually has clinically relevant effects. However, many reported effects of vitamin C increase the plausibility of clinically relevant effects. This is a selection of relevant reviews.

Vitamin C and the immune system

The old reviews show that there was great interest in the effects of vitamin C on infections soon after the vitamin was identified.

Clausen SW. The influence of nutrition upon resistance to infection. *Physiol Rev.* 1934;14:309–50.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14497214> <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.1934.14.3.309>

Robertson EC. The vitamins and resistance to infection: Vitamin C. *Medicine.* 1934;13:190–206.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14496927> <https://doi.org/10.1097/00005792-193405000-00001>

Perla D, Marmorston J. Role of vitamin C in resistance. Parts I and II.

Archives in Pathology. 1937;23:543–75, 683–712.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14527877>

Glazebrook AJ, Thomson S. The administration of vitamin C in a large institution and its effect on general health and resistance to infection. *J Hyg (Lond).* 1942;42(1):1-19. [4-page introduction summarized the field]

<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0022172400012596> <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2199803>

Bourne GH. Vitamin C and immunity. *Br J Nutr.* 1949;2(4):341-7. <https://doi.org/10.1079/BJN19480063>

Thomas WR, Holt PG. Vitamin C and immunity: an assessment of the evidence.

Clin Exp Immunol. 1978;32(2):370-9. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1541262>

Gross RL, Newberne PM. Role of nutrition in immunologic function [vitamin C: 255-60,290-302].

Physiol Rev. 1980;60(1):188-302. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.1980.60.1.188>

Jariwalla RJ, Harakeh S. Antiviral and immunomodulatory activities of ascorbic acid.

Subcell Biochem. 1996;25:213-231. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4613-0325-1_11

Webb AL, Villamor E. Update: Effects of antioxidant and non-antioxidant vitamin supplementation on immune function. *Nutr Rev.* 2007;65:181–217. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1753-4887.2007.tb00298.x>

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/227691959>

Manning J, et al. Vitamin C promotes maturation of T-cells.

Antioxid Redox Signal. 2013;19:2054–67. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ars.2012.4988>

Carr AC, Maggini S. Vitamin C and immune function.

Nutrients. 2017;9:1211. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu9111211>

Ang A, et al. Vitamin C and immune cell function in inflammation and cancer.

Biochem Soc Trans. 2018;46:1147–59. <https://doi.org/10.1042/BST20180169>

Biochemistry of vitamin C

Englard S, Seifter S. The biochemical functions of ascorbic acid.

Annu Rev Nutr. 1986;6:365–406. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.nu.06.070186.002053>

Mandl J, et al. Vitamin C: Update on physiology and pharmacology.

Br J Pharmacol. 2009;157:1097–110. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1476-5381.2009.00282.x>

May JM, Harrison FE. Role of vitamin C in the function of the vascular endothelium.

Antioxid Redox Signal. 2013;19:2068–83. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ars.2013.5205>

Young JI, et al. Regulation of the epigenome by vitamin C.

Annu Rev Nutr. 2015;35:545–64. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-nutr-071714-034228>

Padayatty SJ, Levine M. Vitamin C: The known and the unknown and Goldilocks.

Oral Dis. 2016;22:463–93. <https://doi.org/10.1111/odi.12446>

Brabson JP, et al. Epigenetic regulation of genomic stability by vitamin C.

Front Genet. 2021;12:675780. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2021.675780>

Statistical issues

mid-P

In 2×2 tables, when there are only a few cases in one group, the mid-P value is the most appropriate method to calculate the P values for the differences in the treatment groups [S1-S4]. Table 7 from [S1] illustrates the rationalization, see below. The mid-P was used when comparing groups with small numbers of cases.

S1. Hemilä H. Do vitamins C and E affect respiratory infections? University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland 2006: p.21 (Table 7) [see below].

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6395595>

S2. Lancaster HO. Significance tests in discrete distributions. J Am Stat Assoc. 1961;56:223-34.

<https://doi.org/10.2307/2282247>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/2282247>

S3. Berry G, Armitage P. Mid-P confidence intervals. Statistician. 1995;44:417-23.

<https://doi.org/10.2307/2348891>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/2348891>

S4. Lydersen S, Fagerland MW, Laake P. Recommended tests for association in 2 x 2 tables.

Stat Med. 2009;28(7):1159–75.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.3531>

Table 7. Rationalization of the mid-P-value

Let us assume that we observe results forming the following 2x2 table:

1	1
1	1

In the Fisher exact test, we calculate the probability of all tables that have the same fixed margins (3 tables in this case):

	Probability of the table:				
<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	2	0	0	2	P[up] = 1/6
2	0				
0	2				
<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1	1	1	1	P[obs] = 4/6
1	1				
1	1				
<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	0	2	2	0	P[low] = 1/6
0	2				
2	0				

The lower 1-tailed ‘Fisher P’ adds the probabilities of the observed table (P[obs]) and the probabilities of the tables of the lower tail.

Thus here,

$$\text{Fisher } P[1-t] = 4/6 + 1/6 = 5/6 = 0.833.$$

The lower 1-tailed ‘mid-P’ adds half of the probability of the observed table ($\frac{1}{2} \times P[\text{obs}]$) and the probabilities of the tables of the lower tail.

Thus here,

$$\text{mid-P}[1-t] = 2/6 + 1/6 = 3/6 = 0.5.$$

With the ‘observed table’ having 1 observation in each cell, there is no evidence of any difference from the null effect, and we should expect the corresponding P[1-t] to be exactly 0.5. In this respect the mid-P corresponds to scaling the P-value so that P[1-t] = 0.5 corresponds to the null effect. Thus the mid-P modification is consistent with the t-test, which also yields P[1-t] = 0.5 if there is no difference between the groups, so that their means are equal.

The 1-tailed mid-P-values never add up to a 2-tailed mid-P-value above 1. In contrast, the 1-tailed Fisher P-values may add up to the 2-tailed Fisher P-value above 1 as in the case above (Fisher P[2-t] = 2 x 0.833 = 1.67); however, P values above 1 are inconsistent with the concept of probability.

1-tailed P

P(1-tail)-values are shown in this review, since the main question is whether vitamin C supplementation decreases the incidence or severity of respiratory infections or not, and this question is unidirectional. When pertinent, the 2-tailed P-value is given, and in such a case the 2-tails are explicitly mentioned as P(2-tail). If the P(1-tail) is greater than about 0.97, then there is a reason to assume harm in the treatment group of the particular trial.

Relative scale: Ratio of Means (RoM)

It has been shown that the relative scale much better captures the effect of treatments on many continuous outcomes such as the duration of colds [S5-S9]. The ratio of means is a useful scale to compare two groups [S5].

S5. Friedrich JO, Adhikari NK, Beyene J. Ratio of means for analyzing continuous outcomes in meta-analysis performed as well as mean difference methods. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2011;64:556–64.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2010.09.016>

S6. Hemilä H. Many continuous variables such as the duration of the common cold should be analyzed using the relative scale. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2016;78:128-9.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2016.03.020>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/173096>

S7. Hemilä H. Duration of the common cold and similar continuous outcomes should be analyzed on the relative scale: a case study of two zinc lozenge trials. *BMC Med Res. Methodol.* 2017;17(1):82.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-017-0356-y>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5427521>

S8. Hemilä H, Chalker E, Tukiainen J. Quantile treatment effect of zinc lozenges on common cold duration: a novel approach to analyze the effect of treatment on illness duration. *Front Pharmacol.* 2022;13:817522.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.817522>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8844493>

S9. Hemilä H, Pirinen M. Estimating quantile treatment effect on the original scale of the outcome variable: a case study of common cold treatments. *Arxiv.* 2023 Oct.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2310.17917>

Multiple comparison issues

Some of the trial reports published several P-values.

In Table V, Ludvigsson (1977) [28] published 12 P-values for the “Pilot trial” and 12 P-values for the “Main trial”, i.e., 24 P-values in one single table. The set of 12 outcomes were composed of 3 different common cold definitions and 4 different outcomes (free from symptoms, incidence, duration, and the product between incidence and duration).

When we expect – purely by chance – on average one “significant” ($P < 0.05$) P-value per 20 independent measurements, the two significant P-values in Ludvigsson’s Table V might be explained just by chance.

On the other hand, the effect on “Duration of absence from school” per episode $Z = 2.42$ corresponds to $P(1\text{-tail}) = 0.008$ [Main trial] “Duration of upper respiratory tract infection” per episode $Z = 3.05$ corresponds to $P(1\text{-tail}) = 0.001$ [Pilot trial]

These are much lower than the (arbitrary) limit of $P = 0.05$.

$P = 0.008$ would require about 125 independent P-value calculations to explain the finding just by chance.

$P = 0.001$ would require about 1000 independent P-value calculations to explain the finding just by chance.

Therefore, it is unlikely that the P-values reported by Ludvigsson are just examples of random variation.

Furthermore, of the 2×12 P-values for the two trials, 2×3 were for the outcome “totally free from symptoms”, 2×3 were for common cold incidence, 2×3 were for the duration of episodes, and 2×3 were for the product between incidence and duration. Both the small P-values were for the duration of episodes and this is consistent with the pooled results in our Cochrane review (2013) [5]. None of the 2×3 measures on incidence of colds found a significant benefit, which is also consistent with the pooled results in our Cochrane review (2013) [5]. Thus, although Ludvigsson (1977) calculated several P-values, the 2 positive findings corresponded to particularly small P-values in the group of 6 P-values, and they were consistent with the other trials reporting on vitamin C for common cold duration.

Anderson (1972) [30] also calculated several P-values in Table II, and in that case the results were also consistent with the findings in our Cochrane review (2013). Thus, also in that case, the significant P-values were not explained by multiple comparisons.

Source of data and P-values for Table 2

Elwood (1976) [23] Table III:

<https://doi.org/10.1136/jech.30.3.193>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc478963>

Women living in South Wales, UK, who were involved in a nutrition study on their children who had had a child within the previous two years, and were not again pregnant.

Placebo	349
Vitamin C	339

Placebo	424 "Simple colds"
Vitamin C	416 "Simple colds"
RR	1.01

Placebo	266 "Chest colds"
Vitamin C	211 "Chest colds"
RR	0.817
P	0.028

```
#Elwood chest colds
> poisson.test(c(211, 266), c(339, 349))
Comparison of Poisson rates
data: c(211, 266) time base: c(339, 349)
count1 = 211, expected count1 = 235.03, p-value = 0.02798
alternative hypothesis: true rate ratio is not equal to 1
95 percent confidence interval: 0.6783813 0.9820592
sample estimates: rate ratio 0.8166323
> (P_1tail=0.02798/2)
[1] 0.01399
```

Placebo	6.38 days duration of all colds
Vitamin C	5.97 days duration of all colds
Decrease	-6.4%

Ludvigsson (1977) [24] Table V, the Main Study:

<https://www.academia.edu/69567236>

<https://doi.org/10.3109/inf.1977.9.issue-2.07>

The study was conducted in a Swedish district with a high population of children and a known high frequency of infections. Schoolchildren in Sweden, Participants were from two schools and aged 8-9 years.

Placebo	311
Vitamin C	304
Placebo	2.00 Incidence for “Cold symptoms from the nose”
Vitamin C	2.14 Incidence for “Cold symptoms from the nose”
RR	1.07
Placebo	0.72 Incidence for “Absence from school because of upper respiratory tract infection”
Vitamin C	0.74 Incidence for “Absence from school because of upper respiratory tract infection”
RR	1.03
Placebo	5.67 days of “Cold symptoms from the nose” per episode
Vitamin C	6.04 days of “Cold symptoms from the nose” per episode
Increase	+6.5%
Placebo	3.22 days of “Absence from school because of upper respiratory tract infection” per episode
Vitamin C	2.77 days of “Absence from school because of upper respiratory tract infection” per episode
Decrease	-14.0%
P	0.008 [Table V: t = 2.42]

Pitt (1979) [25] Table 2:

<https://www.academia.edu/78271637>

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1979.03290350028016>

US male marine recruits who underwent 11 weeks of recruit training during October, November and December. Vitamin C administration was begun in the 3rd week of training.

Placebo	343
Vitamin C	331

Placebo	1.80 colds per person
Vitamin C	1.81 colds per person
Increase	+0.6%

Placebo	11.5 days per cold
Vitamin C	11.2 days per cold
Decrease	-2.6%

Placebo	1.97 severity score
Vitamin C	1.87 severity score

The severity of colds was classified on a numerical rating from 1 to 4. Since the minimum of their scale was 1, for our analysis we rescaled the severity levels for the range from 0 to 3 [16].

Therefore,

Placebo	0.97 severity score corrected
Vitamin C	0.87 severity score corrected
Decrease	-10.3%
P	0.012 [Table 2: $\text{Chi}^2(15 \text{ df}) = 27.8$, which corresponds to $P(2\text{-tail}) = 0.023$]

Placebo	7 cases of pneumonia
Vitamin C	1 case of pneumonia
RR	0.14
P	0.022 [6]

Cases of pneumonia (p.910):

“Pneumonia developed in eight recruits, and only one of these recruits was from the vitamin C group ($P < .04$). Each of these eight recruits had typical roentgenographic and physical signs of pneumonitis, although five recruits were febrile, and only four recruits had elevated WBC counts. Pneumococci were isolated from the sputum in three recruits and seen intracellularly on Gram's stain in two other recruits. Two of these recruits also had fourfold increases in parainfluenza titers”.

In the Pitt (1979) trial, the proportion of participants who recognized vitamin C from subjective observations was calculated in [1, p.26, Table 11].

(p.910):

“Which Pill?—When asked which pill they thought they were taking, 53% of the recruits in each group stated that they did not know. Of those who replied either vitamin C or placebo, the reasons given were that their health either was or was not better, that they did or did not have colds, or that the pills did or did not taste as they expected vitamin C might. Based on these reasons, 27% of the vitamin C group and 26% of the placebo group correctly stated which pill they were taking. Twenty percent of the vitamin C group and 21% of the placebo group guessed incorrectly and for the same reasons, and these differences were not statistically significant”

(p.908):

“the placebo tablets were formulated from citric acid and were indistinguishable in appearance and taste from the vitamin C tablets...

pill taking was supervised and observed by the drill instructors in each platoon. Neither the recruits or drill instructors nor the physicians and corpsmen who treated the recruits were aware of which pill any individual recruit was taking.”

Therefore, our interpretation is that the identification of vitamin C was based on subjective observations caused by physiological effects.

Anderson (1972) [26] Table II:

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1940935>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1941144> [correction 1]

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1941189> [correction 2]

Canadian volunteers were sought from a variety of occupations and age groups in order to obtain a reasonable cross-section of the general population. Persons were asked not to enrol unless they normally experienced at least 1 cold in the period January to March and so were not representative of the general population in terms of susceptibility to colds.

Placebo 411 subjects

Vitamin C 407 subjects

Placebo 4.18 symptom days per cold episode

Vitamin C 3.96 symptom days per cold episode

Decrease -5.3%

Placebo 1.32 days confined to house per **cold episode**

Vitamin C 1.04 days confined to house per **cold episode**

Decrease -21.2%

P 0.0071 [Table II: t = 2.45]

Placebo 1.87 days confined to house per **subject**

Vitamin C 1.30 days confined to house per **subject**

Decrease -30.5%

P 0.00043 [Table II: t =3.33]

Placebo 76 free of illness throughout the study

Vitamin C 105 free of illness throughout the study

Difference +7.3 percentage points [1, p.44].

P 0.006 [1, p.44, Table 20].

(p.505):

“any illness during the trial period”

“In the vitamin group 105 subjects (26%) remained free of illness throughout the study, while the corresponding figure for the placebo group was 76 (18%).”

Table III reported incidence of “Nose” and “Throat” colds

However, these data were corrected later:

Anderson TW, Reid DB, Beaton GH. Vitamin C and the common cold [Correction].

Can Med Assoc J. 1973;108(2):133.

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1941144/>

The corrected Table III:

Placebo 0.84 “Nose colds” per subject
Vitamin C 0.82 “Nose colds” per subject
Ratio reported: 98%; indicating decrease by -2%

Placebo 0.43 “Throat colds” per subject
Vitamin C 0.34 “Throat colds” per subject
Ratio reported: 79%; indicating reduction by -21%
0.34/0.43 = 0.7906, corresponding to -20.93%

Accurate data were not reported for Table III data, but the above incidence data gives -20.93% as the difference and we use them for our estimation of P for the difference in “Throat colds”.

Placebo $411 \times 0.43 = 176.7$ “Throat colds” per group
Vitamin C $407 \times 0.34 = 138.4$ “Throat colds” per group

Rounding to:

Placebo 177 “Throat colds” per group
Vitamin C 139 “Throat colds” per group
leads to a difference -20.70% which is consistent with the reported difference, i.e., 79%
P 0.0044

```
> riskratio.wald(AndersonThroat)
$data
      Outcome
Predictor Disease1 Disease2 Total
  Exposed1      139      268    407
  Exposed2      177      234    411
  Total         316      502    818

$measure
      risk ratio with 95% C.I.
Predictor estimate lower upper
  Exposed1 1.0000000 NA NA
  Exposed2 0.8646367 0.7750471 0.9645821

$P.value
      two-sided
Predictor midp.exact fisher.exact chi.square
  Exposed1 NA NA NA
  Exposed2 0.00897108 0.009737317 0.008849191

> (P_1tail=0.00897108/2)
[1] 0.00448554
```

Anderson (1972) reported in Tables I and IV data useful for the subgroup analyses by

- Contacts with children (Yes/No)
- Usual colds (0-1 vs 2+)

The reported data were analyzed in [16], indicating significant subgroup differences.

This is the calculation of the P-values within the two subgroups in which vitamin C was effective by the Ratio of Means approach.

The P-value for the Sabiston (1974) trial is calculated for Figure 5.

The Friedrich data [S5] is used as an example.

```
ROM
      Study  Ne      Me      Se  Nc      Mc  Sc
1      Friedrich  9 213.00 67.00  10 177.00 40.0
2      Sabiston 1974  6  0.80  0.80  14  2.40  2.1
3  Anderson 1972 Yng childs 140  1.31  2.04 148  2.43  2.8
4  Anderson 1972 Freq colds 211  1.31  2.04 192  2.29  2.8
> ROM$LnROM = log(ROM$Me/ROM$Mc)
> ROM$SDe = (ROM$Se/ROM$Me)**2/ROM$Ne
> ROM$SDc = (ROM$Sc/ROM$Mc)**2/ROM$Nc
> ROM$SElnROM = sqrt(ROM$SDe + ROM$SDc)
> ROM$z = ROM$LnROM/ROM$SElnROM
> ROM$p = pnorm(ROM$z)
> #ROM$CIlo = exp(ROM$LnROM - 1.96*ROM$SElnROM)
> ROM
      Study  Ne      Me      Se  Nc      Mc  Sc  LnROM  SDe  SDc  SElnROM  z  p
1      Friedrich  9 213.00 67.00  10 177.00 40.0  0.185 0.0110 0.00511  0.127  1.46 9.28e-01
2      Sabiston 1974  6  0.80  0.80  14  2.40  2.1 -1.099 0.1667 0.05469  0.470 -2.34 9.77e-03
3  Anderson 1972 Yng childs 140  1.31  2.04 148  2.43  2.8 -0.618 0.0173 0.00896  0.162 -3.81 6.82e-05
4  Anderson 1972 Freq colds 211  1.31  2.04 192  2.29  2.8 -0.559 0.0115 0.00777  0.139 -4.03 2.83e-05
```

Calculation of NNT for Table 3

These data were collected for the Cochrane review (2013) [5].

```
Stress
  studlab event.e n.e event.c n.c
1  Moolla 1996      4 13      13 19
2  Peters 1993     14 43      28 41
3  Peters 1996      7 44      19 47
4  Sabiston 1974    6 56      14 56
5  Ritzel 1961     17 139     31 140
> Stress$Inci.e <- Stress$event.e/Stress$n.e
> Stress$Inci.c <- Stress$event.c/Stress$n.c
> Stress$Difference <- Stress$Inci.c -Stress$Inci.e
> Stress$NNT <- 1/Stress$Difference
> Stress$RR <- Stress$Inci.e/Stress$Inci.c
> Stress$NNT_fromRR <- 1/( Stress$Inci.c - 0.4752*Stress$Inci.c )
> Stress
  studlab event.e n.e event.c n.c Inci.e Inci.c Difference  NNT  RR NNT_fromRR
1  Moolla 1996      4 13      13 19 0.308 0.684 0.3765 2.66 0.450 2.78
2  Peters 1993     14 43      28 41 0.326 0.683 0.3573 2.80 0.477 2.79
3  Peters 1996      7 44      19 47 0.159 0.404 0.2452 4.08 0.394 4.71
4  Sabiston 1974    6 56      14 56 0.107 0.250 0.1429 7.00 0.429 7.62
5  Ritzel 1961     17 139     31 140 0.122 0.221 0.0991 10.09 0.552 8.61
```

The pooled effect 0.4752 originates from the meta-analysis:

```
StressMA <- metabin(event.e,n.e,event.c,n.c, studlab, data=Stress, random=F, sm ="RR")
```

```
StressMA
```

```
Number of studies combined: k = 5
```

```
Number of observations: o = 598
```

```
Number of events: e = 153
```

```

          RR          95%-CI      z  p-value
Common effect model 0.4752 [0.3549; 0.6364] -4.99 < 0.0001
```

```
Quantifying heterogeneity:
```

```
tau^2 = 0 [0.0000; 0.0246]; tau = 0 [0.0000; 0.1567]
```

```
I^2 = 0.0% [0.0%; 79.2%]; H = 1.00 [1.00; 2.19]
```

```
Test of heterogeneity:
```

```
  Q d.f. p-value
  0.60 4 0.9633
```

```
Details on meta-analytical method:
```

```
- Mantel-Haenszel method
```

```
- Restricted maximum-likelihood estimator for tau^2
```

```
- Q-Profile method for confidence interval of tau^2 and tau
```

Cox regression analysis of the COVID A to Z trial for Figure 3

The data were previously extracted [63] from the COVID A to Z trial report [62].

```
> table(COVIDAZ)
```

```
, , Cured = 0
```

Day	0	1
2	0	0
3	0	0
4	0	0
5	0	0
6	0	0
7	0	0
8	0	0
9	0	0
10	0	0
11	0	0
12	0	0
15	0	0
16	0	0
23	0	0
25	0	0
28	6	2

```
, , Cured = 1
```

Day	0	1
2	6	2
3	7	13
4	3	8
5	6	5
6	1	5
7	4	4
8	2	4
9	7	2
10	2	1
11	2	0
12	1	1
15	1	0
16	1	0
23	1	0
25	0	1
28	0	0

```
COVIDAZs <- Surv(COVIDAZ$Day, COVIDAZ$Cured)
```

```
> COVIDAZs
```

```
[1] 2 2 3 3 3 3 3 3 3 3 3 3 3 3 4 4 4 4 4 4 4 4 4 4 5 5
[26] 5 5 5 6 6 6 6 6 7 7 7 7 8 8 8 8 9 9 10 12 25 28+ 28+ 2 2
[51] 2 2 2 2 3 3 3 3 3 3 3 4 4 4 5 5 5 5 5 5 6 7 7 7 7 7
[76] 8 8 9 9 9 9 9 9 9 10 10 11 11 12 15 16 23 28+ 28+ 28+ 28+ 28+ 28+
```

```
> COVIDAZ_Cox <- coxph(COVIDAZs ~ COVIDAZ$vitC, ties="exact")
```

```
> COVIDAZ_Cox
```

```
Call:
```

```
coxph(formula = COVIDAZs ~ COVIDAZ$vitC, ties = "exact")
```

	coef	exp(coef)	se(coef)	z	p
COVIDAZ\$vitC	0.5291	1.6974	0.2362	2.24	0.0251

```
Likelihood ratio test=5.02 on 1 df, p=0.0251
```

```
n= 98, number of events= 90
```

```
> confint(COVIDAZ_Cox)
```

```
2.5 % 97.5 %
COVIDAZ$vitC 0.0662379 0.9920139
```

```
> exp(confint(COVIDAZ_Cox))
```

```
2.5 % 97.5 %
COVIDAZ$vitC 1.068481 2.69666
```

Calculation of mid-P values for the pneumonia treatment trials

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6406235>

```
> riskratio.wald(Hunt)
$data
      Outcome
Predictor Disease1 Disease2 Total
Exposed1      24         5     29
Exposed2      27         1     28
Total         51         6     57

$measure
      risk ratio with 95% C.I.
Predictor estimate lower upper
Exposed1      1.0000      NA     NA
Exposed2      0.2071 0.02579 1.664

$p.value
      two-sided
Predictor midp.exact fisher.exact chi.square
Exposed1      NA         NA         NA
Exposed2      0.1178      0.1936     0.09272

> (P_ltail=0.1178/2)
[1] 0.0589
```

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-021-06288-0>

```
> riskratio.wald(Mahmoodpoor)
$data
      Outcome
Predictor Disease1 Disease2 Total
Exposed1      29         12     41
Exposed2      34         7     41
Total         63         19     82

$measure
      risk ratio with 95% C.I.
Predictor estimate lower upper
Exposed1      1.0000      NA     NA
Exposed2      0.5833 0.2555 1.332

$p.value
      two-sided
Predictor midp.exact fisher.exact chi.square
Exposed1      NA         NA         NA
Exposed2      0.205      0.2951     0.1906

> (P_ltail=0.205/2)
[1] 0.1025
```

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-37934-z>

```
> riskratio.wald(Chambers)
$data
      Outcome
Predictor Disease1 Disease2 Total
Exposed1      37         2     39
Exposed2      36         0     36
Total         73         2     75

$measure
      risk ratio with 95% C.I.
Predictor estimate lower upper
Exposed1         1      NA     NA
Exposed2         0         0   NaN

$p.value
      two-sided
Predictor midp.exact fisher.exact chi.square
Exposed1      NA         NA         NA
Exposed2      0.267      0.4941     0.1684

> (P_ltail=0.267/2)
[1] 0.1335
```

Variations in vitamin C levels in the control and vitamin C groups: data for Figure 5

Trial	Control group vitamin C (g/day)			Vitamin C group vitamin C (g/day)	
	Diet	Supplement	Total	Supplement	Total
Anderson (1974)		4	4	4	8
Karlowski (1975)		3	3	3	6
Miller (1977)	0.48 ^{a)}	0.050	0.53	1.0	1.53
Mochalkin (1970)		0.525	0.525	0.525	1.05
Peters (1993) Runners	0.285 ^{b)}	0.209 ^{c)}	0.494	0.6	1.139
Peters (1993) Sedentary	0.242 ^{b)}	0.038 ^{c)}	0.280	0.6	0.783
Himmelstein (1998) Runners	0.169	0.209 ^{c)}	0.378	1	1.442
Himmelstein (1998) Sedentary	0.149	0.078 ^{c)}	0.227	1	1.312
Pitt (1979)	0.15 ^{a)}		0.15	2	2.15
Ludvigsson (1977) Pilot	0.16 ^{a)}	0.03	0.19	1	1.16
Ludvigsson (1977) Main	0.16 ^{a)}	0.01	0.17	1	1.16
Carr (1981)	0.1	0.07	0.17	1	1.1
Baird (1977)	0.050		0.050	0.080	0.130
Sabiston (1974)	0.039		0.039	1	1.04
Glazebrook (1942)	0.0125		0.0125	0.2	0.21

^{a)} Dietary intake was estimated from reported blood or urine vitamin C levels (see below), or was assumed (Carr 1981).

^{b)} Calculated from the published Total and Supplement doses.

^{c)} Supplementation by one's own initiative (Peters 1993; Himmelstein 1998).

Sources of the data:

Anderson (1974) [46]: This was an 8-arm trial, we show the comparison between arms #7 and #8. For the greater proportion of short 1-day colds in the 8 g/day group, the P-value was $P(1\text{-tail}) = 0.023$, see calculation in [1, p.42, Table 19].

The P-value for the trend over the duration of colds over the placebo arm #4 and vitamin C arms #7 and #8 (i.e. 0, 4, and 8 g/day) was calculated in [2], see the justification for the placebo group #4 in [1, p.40, Table 16]. For the linear regression over the 3 data points, a $P(1\text{-tail})$ for trend = 0.007 [2].

Karlowski (1975) [45]: There were 2 vitamin C arms with 3 g/day, and 1 arm with 6 g/day. One of the 3 g/day arms was administered vitamin C regularly over the trial, and another was administered for 5 days when a common cold occurred. The 6 g/day was treated with both protocols (i.e. 3 + 3 g/day).

The trend for the effect of vitamin C on the duration of colds was calculated over the placebo arm and 3 and 6 g/day vitamin C arms:

Variance analysis based on the reported SD values gave a P(1-tail) for trend = 0.02 [49].

For the linear regression over the 4 data points, a P(1-tail) for trend < 0.009 [2,50].

The Karlowski trial was erroneously analyzed, see [1,48] and

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225873>

Miller (1977) [89]

See the estimation of baseline vitamin C intake below.

Miller also administered 50 mg/day to both trial groups with the following reasoning:

“All twins received a multiple vitamin preparation that contained 50 mg of vitamin C in order to ensure that any observed treatment effect could reasonably be attributed to pharmacologic doses of the vitamin rather than to dietary deficiency” (p.248-9).

However, administration of vitamin C to the control group confounds the comparison. It is possible that the usual dietary intake of vitamin C does not lead to maximal function of the immune system, but this cannot be tested properly when the placebo group is given a vitamin C supplement.

Inferring vitamin C by mothers of the twins:

“As a final approach to the detection of subtle treatment effects on general well-being that might not have been measured by any of our tests, each mother was asked to guess, while she and the investigator were still blinded, which twin had received the vitamin. Twenty-three of the 44 mothers could not tell any difference between the treated and control twins. However, among the 21 mothers who felt there was a detectable effect of treatment, 17 correctly identified the twin who had received the vitamin ($P < 0.05$). Among the mothers of the young twins in whom the objective evidence for a treatment effect was the greatest, eight of nine guessed correctly ($P < 0.02$)” (p.250.)

For the 4/17 split, the binomial distribution gives P(1-tail) = 0.004:

```
> binom.test(17, 21, p = 0.5, alternative = "greater")
Exact binomial test
data: 17 and 21
number of successes = 17, number of trials = 21, p-value = 0.003599
alternative hypothesis: true probability of success is greater than 0.5
```

Of the 44 mothers, 4 mothers guessed the treatment incorrectly and that needs to be subtracted from the 21 mothers who gave the correct answer (compare analysis in [1, p.26, Table 11]. Thus, we conclude that 39% (17/44) of the mothers could infer the administration of vitamin C correctly.

For the 1/8 split among the mothers of the young twins, the binomial distribution gives P(1-tail) = 0.02:

```
> binom.test(8, 9, p = 0.5, alternative = "greater")
Exact binomial test
data: 8 and 9
number of successes = 8, number of trials = 9, p-value = 0.01953
```

Mochalkin (1970) [9], see summary and calculation in [6]. The ranges for vitamin C doses were 0.25-0.8 g/day in the low dose group and 0.5-1.6 g/day in the high dose group. We use the mid-point doses in the table above.

Peters (1993) [32].

Baseline daily vitamin C intake is reported in Table 1.

Mean supplement on own initiative is reported in Table 2, but there is no separate report of dietary vitamin C intake.

Runners vitamin C group:

Supplement on own initiative 227 mg/day (included in the 547 mg/day below)

Total baseline vitamin C: 547 mg/day

Runners placebo group:

Supplement on own initiative 209 mg/day

Total baseline vitamin C: 494 mg/day

Sedentary vitamin C group:

Supplement on own initiative 35 mg/day

Total baseline vitamin C: 194 mg/day

Sedentary placebo group:

Supplement on own initiative 38 mg/day

Total baseline vitamin C: 280 mg/day

Calculation of the P-value for Figure 5:

```
> riskratio.wald(Peters)
$data
      Outcome
Predictor Disease1 Disease2 Total
Exposed1      14       29     43
Exposed2      28       13     41
Total         42       42     84

$measure
      risk ratio with 95% C.I.
Predictor estimate      lower      upper
Exposed1  1.000000         NA         NA
Exposed2  0.470143  0.2866128  0.7711951

$p.value
      two-sided
Predictor midp.exact fisher.exact  chi.square
Exposed1          NA          NA          NA
Exposed2  0.001233025  0.002055608  0.001059629

> (P_1tail=0.00123/2)
[1] 0.000615
```

Himmelstein (1998) [S10]

Baseline vitamin C intake is reported in Table 2.

Runners vitamin C group:

Mean dietary intake 207 mg/day

Supplement on own initiative 234 mg/day

Total baseline vitamin C: 442 mg/day

Runners placebo group:

Mean dietary intake 169 mg/day

Supplement on own initiative 209 mg/day

Total baseline vitamin C: 378 mg/day

Sedentary vitamin C group:

Mean dietary intake 210 mg/day

Supplement on own initiative 102 mg/day

Total baseline vitamin C: 312 mg/day

Sedentary placebo group:

Mean dietary intake 149 mg/day

Supplement on own initiative 78 mg/day

Total baseline vitamin C: 227 mg/day

S10. Himmelstein SA, Robergs RA, Koehler KM, Lewis SL, Qualls CR.
Vitamin C supplementation and upper respiratory tract infections in marathon runners.
J Exerc Physiol Online. 1998;1(2):1–21.
<https://www.asep.org/asep/asep/jan9.htm>
<https://www.academia.edu/66783857>
Dissertation:
<https://www.proquest.com/docview/304251290>

Pitt (1979) [25]

See the estimation of the baseline vitamin C intake below.
See the P-values described for Table 2 above.

Ludvigsson (1977) [24]

See the estimation of the baseline vitamin C intake below.
See the P-values described for Table 2 above.

Placebo groups were administered vitamin C in the Pilot and Main trials::

“In one of the groups the children received daily a fizzy tablet which contained 1000 mg vitamin C; in the other group the fizzy tablet looked and tasted the same but contained 30 mg vitamin C in the spring study [small “Pilot study”] and 10 mg in the autumn study [large “Main study”].”

Carr (1981) [88] wrote in the methods that *“both groups received multivitamin capsules containing 70 mg vitamin C. This was to ensure that any observed treatment effect could reasonably be attributed to the pharmacologic dose of vitamin C and not to alleviation of dietary deficiency.”*

However, administration of vitamin C to the control group confounds the comparison. It is possible that the usual dietary intake of vitamin C does not lead to maximal function of the immune system, but this cannot be tested properly when the placebo group is given a vitamin C supplement.

In Table 2, Carr (1981) reported a significant ($P[2\text{-tail}] < 0.01$) effect on the average duration of colds in twins living apart (4.86 vs. 7.50 days) and we may ask whether the difference would have been even greater if the placebo group had not been administered 70 mg/day of vitamin C.

In the table above we assume that the dietary intake was 0.1 g/day.

Baird (1977) [39] wrote in their introduction: *“In the current study, designed primarily as a prophylactic one, a daily supplement of 80 mg of AA was used; the estimated daily intake from dietary sources was 50 mg, thus giving a total daily intake of about 130 mg.”*

Sabiston (1974) [34] wrote (p.4): *“it was determined that the RP-4 rations (1970-71) on which the men were living, apparently provided a maximum of 37–41 mg Vitamin C per day in a single fruit-drink mix. As previous observations suggested that the fruit-drink mix was an unpopular item in the rations and tended to be discarded, it appeared that the individual intake of Vitamin C could be below the recommended daily allowance.”*

(p.7): *“One further point with reference to Table 8 is the rather surprising number of men who demonstrated whole-blood ascorbate levels lower than 0.50 mg%. This value is generally taken to indicate the threshold of a possible sub-clinical scorbutic condition.”*

We use 0.039 g/day as an estimated baseline vitamin C intake in the Sabiston (1974) trial, though according to the text above, this is likely to be more than many men were receiving.

Glazebrook (1942) [37] wrote (p.5): “The total intake of vitamin C varied from about 10 to 15 mg. per student per day.”

(p.7): “Pure ascorbic acid powder was added to the diet of a group of boys numbering 350, whose average age was 16. Initially, 200 mg. per day were given to each boy,”

(p.8): “On the 28th day the dosage was reduced to 50 mg. twice a day [i.e. 100 mg/day]”
 “A fresh group of boys was observed, and the initial dosage was increased to 150 mg. twice a day [i.e. 300 mg/day]. Figures indicative of saturation were obtained on the 15th day, and subsequently the dose was reduced to 25 mg. twice a day [i.e. 50 mg/day], when an excretion level approximating to the normal adult level was maintained.”

“A third batch of boys was examined. In this batch all the boys selected were recruits who showed possible clinical evidence of a vitamin C deficiency in the form of a mild gingivo-stomatitis. The ascorbic acid in this case was given in tablet form (Redoxon, Roche Products), in a dosage of 200 mg. once daily.”

We use 0.0125 g/day as the estimated baseline vitamin C intake, and 200 mg/day as the supplement dose which seems to most widely reflect the administered dose.

Findings in the Glazebrook and Thomson (1942) trial [37]

Variable	Placebo	Vitamin C	Difference	P
Participants	1100	335		
Vitamin C dose (mg/day)	10-15	50-300		
Common colds	286	72	-17%	0.047
Colds treated in the Sick Quarters	253	59	-23%	0.017
Days in hospital	6.4	6.32		
Tonsillitis	94	29	0%	
Admitted to hospital	83	18	-30%	0.086
Days in hospital, mean	16.7	10.1	-40%	0.0026
Days in hospital, SD	11.86	6.96		
Days in hospital per infected	14.7	6.3	-57%	0.0021
Pneumonia cases	17	0	-100%	0.0053
Rheumatic fever cases	16	0	-100%	0.007
Days spent in the sick room per boy, mean	4.98	2.5	-50%	<0.00001

See calculations in [21, Appendix 3, p.37].

Estimation of plasma vitamin C levels from reported dietary and urinary vitamin C levels

Mark Levine et al. published a study on vitamin C pharmacokinetics [S11], and their results can be used to estimate dietary vitamin C intake when plasma vitamin C level or change in plasma vitamin C level is reported, see Levine's Figure 1C below.

S11. Levine M, et al. Vitamin C pharmacokinetics in healthy volunteers: evidence for a recommended dietary allowance. Proc Natl Acad Sci USA. 1996;93:3704-3709. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.93.8.3704> <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc39676>

Levine's Figure 1C: Mean level of plasma vitamin C level by dietary intake doses.

Levine's Table 1 gives the data on which the curves in Fig 1C are based and these are the averages for selected doses:

Vitamin C (mg/day)	Mean plasma level (μM)	Compared with 1000 mg/day	Compared with 2500 mg/day	Compared with 60 mg/day
60	24.8	32%	29%	100%
100	56.0	73%	66%	226%
200	65.8	86%	77%	265%
1000	76.9	100%	90%	310%
2500	85.0		100%	343%

The relationship between dietary intake and plasma level can be used to estimate dietary intake if the plasma level is known. Another possible approach to estimate dietary intake is from plasma level differences, which is more robust to differences between plasma vitamin C assay methods.

If a person has vitamin C intake of 60 mg/day, and increases the intake to 2500 mg/day, then the plasma level increases – on average – 3.43-fold (by 243%) based on $85.0/24.8 (= 1/0.29)$.

If a person has vitamin C intake of 100 mg/day, and increases the intake to 2500 mg/day, then the plasma level increases 1.52-fold (by 52%) based on $85/56$.

This relationship can be used to estimate the baseline vitamin C intake, or control group vitamin C intake, when the plasma vitamin C levels are known. We use this approach to estimate the baseline vitamin C intake in the Pitt (1979) and Ludvigsson (1977) trials.

Pitt (1979) [25]

(p.909): “Whole-Blood Ascorbic Acid Levels.—Two determinations of the mean whole-blood ascorbic acid levels of the 234 recruits (103, vitamin C; 131, placebo) were made. There was no significant difference in these levels between the two groups during their first week at Parris Island, 1.00 ± 0.27 mg/dL for recruits taking vitamin C vs 0.98 ± 0.32 mg/dL for recruits taking placebo. After six weeks of pill taking, the vitamin C group had significantly higher ascorbic acid levels (1.36 ± 0.46 mg/dL)”

When participants are administered 2 g/day vitamin C, Levine’s Fig. 1C shows the expected plasma level as 82.4 μ M. Pre-supplementation vitamin C intake level in the vitamin C group can be estimated by the intake that leads to $1.00/1.36 = 73.5\%$ of the plasma level corresponding to a 2 g/day intake level. Measuring with a graphics program from Figure 1C gives 0.15 g/day, which corresponds to 60.6 μ M ($= 0.735\times 82.4$ μ M). Compare also with plasma levels for 100 and 200 mg/day in Levine’s Table 1 on the previous page.

We use 0.15 g/day as the estimated baseline vitamin C intake in the Pitt (1979) trial.

In the above approach, we assume that “Whole-Blood Ascorbic Acid Level” is linearly related to plasma vitamin C level, yet the presence of cells may lead to some inaccuracy.

The Pitt (1979) trial was carried out in “October, November, and December 1974” [25, p. 908] At that period, the US recommendation for vitamin C intake was 0.045 g/day [S12-S14]. Thus, the control group in that trial received 3 times more vitamin C than the recommendation at that time.

S12.

Pauling L. Are recommended daily allowances for vitamin C adequate?

Proc Natl Acad Sci USA. 1974; 71: 4442-4446.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.71.11.4442>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC433902>

S13.

Jukes TH. Further comments on the ascorbic acid requirement.

Proc Natl Acad Sci USA. 1975;72(10):4151-4152.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.72.10.4151>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC433157>

S14.

Harper AE. The recommended dietary allowances for ascorbic acid.

Ann NY Acad Sci. 1975; 258: 491-497.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.1975.tb29307.x>

Ludvigsson (1977) [24]

(p.92): “The main study was supplemented by certain biochemical studies... serum ascorbic acid...”

(p.94): “There was a pronounced difference in serum ascorbic acid between those who received 10 mg and those who received 1000 mg vitamin C daily (86.4 ± 19.1 and 107.0 ± 19.6 mg/dl”

When participants are administered 1 g/day vitamin C, Levine’s Fig. 1C shows the expected plasma level as $77.0 \mu\text{M}$. Placebo-group vitamin C intake level can be estimated by the intake that leads to $86.4/107.0 = 80.7\%$ of the 1 g/day level. Measuring with a graphics program from Figure 1C gives 0.17 g/day, which corresponds to $62.1 \mu\text{M}$ ($= 0.807 \times 77.0 \mu\text{M}$). Compare also with plasma levels for 100 and 200 mg/day in Levine’s Table 1 on the previous page.

The participants in the main study were administered 10 mg/day vitamin C, and that needs to be removed from the 0.17 g/day to reach the dietary intake. We use 0.16 g/day as the estimated dietary vitamin C intake in the Ludvigsson (1977) trial. In addition, the Pilot study administered 30 mg/day and the Main study administered 10 mg/day.

The current (2024) recommendation of vitamin C intake in the USA for 9–13 year-old children is 45 mg [40], and in the UK for 1–10 year-old children is 30 mg [87]. Compared to these levels, the baseline vitamin C intake in the Ludvigsson (1977) trial was 4-5 fold. Thus, the trial does not test whether the recommended dietary intake is sufficient.

Mark Levine et al. [S7] also published the relationship between vitamin C intake and urinary vitamin C excretion, and their findings can be used to estimate dietary vitamin C intake when urinary vitamin C amount is known; see Levine's Figure 4 below.

Levine's Figure 4. The open circles indicate urinary excretion after oral intake, and the closed circles indicate intravenous vitamin C administration. The small figures on the top show the proportion of vitamin C excreted for low doses (A) and for high intravenous doses (B).

Miller (1977) reported in their Table 2 urinary vitamin C excretion before vitamin C administration for 44 twin pairs as 235 mg/day. Measuring with a graphics program from Figure 4 gives 480 mg/day as the dietary intake leading to the excretion of 235 mg/day.

We use 0.48 g/day as the estimated baseline vitamin C intake in the Miller (1977) trial.

Alfred Hess and the risk of pneumonia in vitamin C deficiency

Alfred Hess – a pediatrician in the USA – was the most important clinical investigator of vitamin C deficiency in the early 20th century. He wrote a monograph about scurvy, in which he stated in several parts that there is increased risk of pneumonia in scorbutic animals and humans. These statements are extracted below with their contexts; bold added.

Hess AF. Scurvy: Past and Present. Philadelphia PA: Lippincott USA; 1920.

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505>

<https://digital.library.cornell.edu/catalog/chla2903792>

<https://archive.org/search?query=creator%3A%22Hess+Alfred+Fabian%22>

More relevant parts of Hess' book are extracted in:

Hemilä H. The symptoms of vitamin C deficiency.

1. Observations and descriptions by Hess, Lind, Trotter and Blane.

Zenodo. 2024.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685194>

p.88 [Chapter IV, Pathology of scurvy]

Lungs.—... Edema of the lungs is not uncommon, as we should expect, especially as a terminal condition. **Pneumonia**, lobular or lobar, is one of the most frequent complications and causes of death. Active tuberculosis is a not uncommon secondary manifestation.

p.99 [Chapter IV, Microscopic pathology of scurvy]

Lungs.—Hemorrhages of various size occur in the tissue of the lung or in the air spaces. Hemorrhagic infarcts also have been described, and Sato and Nambu report hyaline degeneration of the blood-vessel walls. Secondary **pneumonias**, usually broncho-pneumonic in type, are of common occurrence, and in many epidemics constitute the prevailing cause of death. Tuberculous lesions are also frequently present, and are stated to assume fresh activity as the result of the nutritional disorder. Edema occurs frequently, the fluid in the acini often containing red blood-cells. Subpleural hemorrhages, thickening of the pleura, purulent or fibrinous pleurisy are common lesions.

p.123 [Chapter V, Experimental scurvy; Guinea pigs]

On opening the chest, slight hemorrhages may be noted in the pericardium and in the visceral and costal pleuræ. The heart is frequently enlarged, and the pericardial sac contains an excess of serum; the right ventricle, however, is not found disproportionately hypertrophied. **Pneumonia** is met with very frequently and constitutes a common terminal infection.

p.179 [Chapter VII, Symptomatology and diagnosis of scurvy]

Nowadays, the disease usually does not reach this stage, and rarely progresses further. If, however, the patient remains untreated, he becomes progressively weaker and more lethargic; there is frequent palpitation, shortness of breath, and increasing loss of weight. The pains in the limbs render him helpless and an object of pity. Marked edema may be added to the picture as the result of starvation, so that the legs become swollen, and even the face becomes bloated. Hemorrhages into the skin as large as the palm of the hand appear on different parts of the body. The gums swell to such an extent that they overlap and may even hide the teeth and protrude from the mouth as foul fungoid growth. Death comes about in various ways. Frequently sudden and fatal syncope occurs, due to heart weakness or to the pouring out of fluid into the pleural or the pericardial cavities. Another frequent cause of death is secondary infection, resulting in **pneumonia**, which finally ends

the suffering of the patient. The fatal outcome is thus described in the narrative of Lord Anson's voyage..."

p.182 [Chapter VII, Symptomatology and diagnosis of scurvy]

Pericarditis, hydrothorax, pleurisy with effusion, **pneumonia**, are common complications of severe forms of scurvy. **Lind reports** that the dominant complication varies in different epidemics; that on one cruise many cases of diarrhoea would occur and on another **many pulmonary infections**.

[see below Lind's section to which Hess refers]

p.202 [Chapter VII, Symptomatology and diagnosis of scurvy]

The main involvement of the respiratory system in scurvy is the polypnoea just described in connection with the cardiorespiratory syndrome. There is no aphonia, a sign so typical of adult and of infantile beriberi, although at times the voice is abnormal and whining. The lungs frequently show some dullness posteriorly, which may be due to engorgement or to the pressure of the enlarged heart. **Pneumonia** is a frequent complication and edema a terminal event. Hydrothorax associated with hydropericardium is of frequent occurrence, and was noted in the early description of this disease in adults and in the first account of Barlow. These effusions rarely progress to what may be termed the clinical degree and under antiscorbutic treatment are rapidly absorbed.

p.217 [Chapter VII, Symptomatology and diagnosis of scurvy]

We have already considered numerous *complications* of scurvy, and shall therefore not go over this ground again. Many of them are due to hemorrhages or to serous effusions in various parts of the body. Another large group in adults as well as in infants are the result of infection. **The respiratory tract is particularly susceptible, pneumonia** constituting the most common cause of death. In infants we meet with frequent attacks of "grippe," widespread occurrence of *nasal diphtheria*, furunculosis and torpid ulcers of the skin, pyelitis, otitis, adenitis, etc. We have encountered nasal diphtheria—with typical bloody mucous discharge—so frequently in connection with scurvy, that where this local infection occurs among a group of infants they should be carefully examined for latent or mild scurvy. Aschoff and Koch recently have laid emphasis on the frequency with which diphtheria complicated scurvy among adults (soldiers). Dysentery is another complication resulting from an invasion of bacteria. Local infections occur more often in adults than in infants—cervical adenitis following gingival pyorrhoea, "bubo" of the groin following infection of the lower extremity, abscess of the calf of the leg following hemorrhage into this region.

p.227 [Chapter VIII, Prognosis of scurvy]

In adults the heart may be weakened by scurvy, and death may result from cardiac failure. Cardiac disturbances occur also in infantile scurvy. This involvement might be expected, in view of the tachycardia (cardiorespiratory phenomenon) which is so frequent a symptom of infantile scurvy. The heart may be rapid for months or even for years after the disorder, and tachycardia may develop on the occasion of even a mild infectious disease. For example, a fever of 101°, due to a common coryza, may cause the heart-beat to rise to perhaps 180 a minute. Children so affected succumb readily to infection, especially to **pneumonia**, which may lead to sudden collapse followed by death.

An important factor in the prognosis of scurvy, as in that of other disorders due to a lack of vitamins, is the marked susceptibility to infection. **Even latent or subacute scurvy causes** a peculiar susceptibility to diphtheria (especially the nasal type), to coryza, bronchitis, and **pneumonia**. A perusal of the literature shows that this susceptibility was noted by the older authors in relation to adults.

Later comments on vitamin C and infections by Hess in 1932:

Hess AF. Recent advances in knowledge of scurvy and the antiscorbutic vitamin. JAMA. 1932;98(17):1429-33.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609694>

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1932.02730430005002>

ASSOCIATION OF SCURVY WITH INFECTIONS

Another point that has been brought into prominence in connection with adult as well as infantile scurvy is its intimate association with the infectious process. In 1917 I stated that "one of the striking and important symptoms of scurvy is a susceptibility to infection (furunculosis, nasal diphtheria, grippe, etc.)." In this connection it may be mentioned that nasal diphtheria was noted among a group of scorbutic infants in spite of the fact that many of them gave a negative Schick reaction. Findlay, attacking the problem from an experimental standpoint, showed that guinea-pigs which suffered from chronic scurvy and showed but few clinical symptoms manifested a decreased resistance to bacterial infection; this he attributed to degenerative changes in the bone marrow. About this time Cramer and Kingsbury emphasized the importance of vitamin A in warding off infections, associating this susceptibility with a decrease in the number of platelets of the blood. Abels, in a monograph on scurvy, stressed this relationship of the scorbutic state to infection, giving the name "dysergie" to the nutritional disturbance which occasions the heightened susceptibility. Recently, Minot and his colleagues came to the conclusion that adult scurvy can be precipitated by infectious processes; in other words, that latent scurvy can by this means be changed to manifest scurvy. In general, therefore, investigations in the laboratory as well as clinical observations are in agreement in stressing the interrelationship of scurvy and bacterial infection.

The 1917 paper:

Hess AF. Infantile scurvy. Part V. A study of its pathogenesis. Am J Dis Child. 1917;14:337-53.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609522>

<https://doi.org/10.1001/archpedi.1917.01910110018002>

Hess AF. Diet, nutrition and infection.
N Engl J Med. 1932;207:637-48.
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In regard to vitamin C, I shall refer only to the bearing of this vitamin on infections, more particularly of the respiratory tract. In 1917, in a paper on the pathogenesis of infantile scurvy, I emphasized the fact that a lack of the antiscorbutic factor which leads to scurvy, at the same time predisposes to infections. This enhanced susceptibility has been confirmed by Abels, Ludwig Meyer and many others. It exists even before the scorbutic signs are manifest in the stage which is better termed "latent scurvy" than "Praeskorbutus" as the abnormal scorbutic state already exists. Similar susceptibility to infections goes hand in hand with adult scurvy. This was pointed out years ago by Lind and others in connection with scurvy in the mercantile marine and among the soldiers in times of war, for example, in our Civil War and in the Crimean War.

But I wish to emphasize quite another aspect of infection in connection with infantile scurvy. In 1917, and again in 1920, I called attention to the "widespread occurrence of nasal diphtheria in infantile scurvy", remarking that "we have encountered nasal diphtheria—with typical bloody mucus discharge—so frequently in connection with scurvy that where this local infection occurs among a group of infants they should be carefully examined for latent or mild scurvy". At the same time I drew attention to the fact that "clinical tests showed that the blood contains sufficient antitoxin (diphtheria) to afford protection." These were the days previous to the use of toxin-antitoxin. Much to our surprise, some of these cases gave a negative Schick test in spite of the definite clinical signs of nasal diphtheria. In two instances the diphtheria

bacilli were tested on guinea pigs and found to be virulent. Not long after these observations an infant died from diphtheria of the larynx which developed although the Schick test was negative. At postmortem a typical membrane was found on the larynx.

Since this time, there has been little opportunity to investigate this subject, as diphtheria has been banished from our institution by the routine use of toxin-antitoxin. Recently, however, we have met with three cases of nasal diphtheria which developed soon after their admission to the institution. These cases were characterized by the typical bloody nasal discharge. In two instances the cultures showed avirulent bacilli, in one which was obtained in December, 1930, the bacilli from the nose were virulent. In spite of this fact, not only was the Schick test negative, but tests carried out in February, 1931, with increasing doses of toxin 1/50-1/40-1/30-1/20-1/10-1/5 M.L.D. all failed to induce a skin reaction. As the result of these experiences we infer that a lack of the antiscorbutic vitamin exerts a local effect on the mucous membrane which diminishes its immunity, but at the same time may not be accompanied by a lowering of systemic immunity. It is probable that a similar phenomenon holds true in connection with a deficiency of vitamin A and that the marked changes in the epithelium, described by Wolbach, bring about a local diminution in resistance. Susceptibility to infections of the skin and of the respiratory tract which occur when this deficiency is marked may be largely a manifestation of a local pathological change.

James Lind and respiratory infections in vitamin C deficiency

James Lind's treatise on scurvy is the most important text on the topic over the ages. However, there was no knowledge of bacteria and X-rays were not available at that time, and for reasons such as these there was no concept of "pneumonia" in the same sense as was known at Hess' times and currently.

See links to several versions of Lind's treatise through:

Hemilä H. The symptoms of vitamin C deficiency.

1. Observations and descriptions by Hess, Lind, Trotter and Blane.

Zenodo. 2024.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685194>

Also:

<https://archive.org/search?query=creator%3A%22Lind+James%22+scurvy>

In our current context, this section to which Hess referred may indicate that in 1747 there were respiratory viruses circulating on the ship, and because of the very low vitamin C levels the sailors did not properly recover from the virus infections and some of them may have suffered from lower respiratory infections as a complication.

On the other hand, in 1746 there may have been viral gastroenteritis circulating so that scurvy caused emphasis on their symptoms.

This is the section to which Hess referred on p. 182, see above.

Lind's text; bold added.

p.110-111 in Lind's 1st edition (Lind's 3rd edition p.105)

I observed a considerable difference in the genius of the disease in the two cruises *ann.* 1746 and 1747. **In the latter, when fevers from cold of the pleuritic and peripneumonic sort prevailed, it tended chiefly to affect the breast with a tightness, oppression, and a hard bound cough, by which a very viscid phlegm was with great difficulty brought up.** The fits of coughing were not constant, but extremely fatiguing ; and this was a universal complaint. Several at this season were feverish ; we had none in a salivation, and the fluxes were mild and manageable.

Whereas in the year 1746, when a different species of diseases prevailed, occasioned by the unwholesome newness of the ship's timbers, and diarrhœas were frequent, the scurvy proved more virulent and fatal. Its worst, most common, and troublesome symptoms, were salivations and dysenteries, especially the latter ; in which one *Nichols* died, and eight or ten more were landed at *Plymouth* in a very low and exhausted condition by it. I did not at that time remark any of them to be feverish, and **their breasts were but slightly affected.**

Albert Szent-Györgyi and pneumonia

Albert Szent-Györgyi was awarded the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine in 1937, partly for isolating vitamin C.

<https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/medicine/1937/szent-gyorgyi>

<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.bi.32.070163.000245>

He was a laboratory scientist and not a clinician. However, a personal experience described by him, while anecdotal, is interesting in the context of our review:

Last year I collected a rather unfortunate personal experience. I broke down with pneumonia which I could not shake off for months, until I discovered that the quantities of ascorbic acid which I took (one gram daily) had become insufficient at my age (84 years). When I went up from one gram to eight, my troubles were over.

Szent-Györgyi A. How new understandings about the biological function of ascorbic acid may profoundly affect our lives. *Exec Health* 1978; 14(8): 1-4.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14627378>

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In another text he considered potential biases in the interpretation of diagnoses:

Another most dangerous pitfall connected with vitamins is in the nature of the action of these substances. This pitfall is responsible for the fact that the real meaning and importance of vitamins is still not sufficiently recognized. This may be illustrated by the following case (concerning vitamin C) which repeats itself yearly by many thousands: Mr. X has a lack of vitamin C and contracts a cold. The cold leads to pneumonia, Mr. X dies and his body is taken to the mortuary, but it is not taken there with the diagnosis “lack of vitamin C,” but with the diagnosis “Pneumonia.” This does not matter for him any more, but matters for the rest of mankind which is misled in its thinking and judgment about vitamins.

Szent-Györgyi A. On a substance that can make us sick (if we do not eat it!). *Exec Health* 1977; 13(8): 16.

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